

Research

Production of fuels and chemicals from biomass: Generated from oil and similar byproducts

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Abstract: Natural frameworks can change over inexhaustible assets, including lignocellulosic biomass, starch harvests, and carbon dioxide, into powers, synthetics, and materials. Ethanol and different items are currently gotten from starch crops, for example, corn. Compound based innovation is being worked on for transformation of lignocellulosic biomass (e.g., wood, grasses, and farming and civil squanders) into fuel ethanol. Biomass derived oil (BDO) reforming with CO₂ was carried out at 800 °C under atmospheric pressure in a tubular fixed bed vertical reactor packed with quartz particles. The feed gas was a mixture of CO₂ and N₂ at various compositions with a flow rate of 30 to 60 cm³ /min. The BDO flow rate was 5 g/h. The item gas comprised generally of H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and C₂H₄. The most extreme creation of blend gas (~76 mol%) was seen at a complete bearer gas stream pace of 60 cm³/min and a mole portion of CO₂ in transporter gas of 0.1. Greatest hydrogen (42 mol%) and H₂ to CO molar proportion (1.44) were acquired while utilizing just N₂ as the transporter gas at a stream pace of 50 cm³/min. In the range of residence time considered, CO₂ was not consumed in BDO gasification at 800 °C but helped to increase gas production at the expense of the char. Pyrolysis of lard was performed to produce a diesel-like liquid and a high heating value gaseous fuel. Lard was fed into the reactor at 5g/h using N₂ (10-70 cm³ /min) as carrier gas. Two particle size ranges of quartz particles (0.7-1.4 and 1.7-2.4 mm) were used as reactor packing material. The liquid product essentially consisted of linear and cyclic alkanes and alkenes, aromatics, ketones, aldehydes and carboxylic acids. The maximum yield for diesel-like liquid product (37g/100g lard) was obtained at 600 °C, residence time of 1.5 s and packing particle size of 1.7- 2.4 mm. The heating value of the product gas ranged between 68 and 165 MJ/m³. This study shows that there is a potential for producing diesel-like liquid from pyrolysis of lard. It also identifies the pyrolysis of animal fats as a source of high heating value gaseous fuel. Steam reforming of lard was performed at 500, 550, 600 and 800 °C and at steam to lard mass ratios of 0.5 to 2.0. The maximum diesel-like liquid yield from the steam reforming process (39 g/100g of lard) was obtained at a steam to lard ratio of 1.5 and a temperature of 600 °C. Higher cetane index (52) and lower viscosity (4.0 mPa.s at 40 °C) were obtained by addition of steam. The net energy recovered was 21.7 and 21.9 kJ /g of lard

respectively from pyrolysis and steam reforming processes. Therefore the processes are energy-efficient. In contrast, lard is a better feedstock than BDO for hydrogen output, char, high heating value gas and high H₂/CO ratio.

Keywords: Biofuel, Biomass, Oil, Lard, Environment friendly

1. Introduction

Maintainable globalization requests extended fuel feedstocks. Within the twentieth century fundamental considers were concentrated on the advancement of cheaply utilize of fossil fills for warm, power (mechanical, commercial and private), transportation powers and chemicals counting pharmaceuticals, cleansers, engineered fiber, plastics, pesticides, fertilizers, greases, dissolvable, waxes, coke, black-top to meet the developing request of the populace (Bender, 2000; Demirbas, 2006; Scott *et al.*, 2010). The transportation sector, moreover, requires considerable supplies of liquid transportation fuel which accounts for a major part of oil reserves. Currently, the fossil resources are not considered as sustainable resources so that it is predicted that oil reserves are relatively depleted by 2025 (Greene *et al.*, 2006). The vast combustion of fossil fuels over the past century has brought serious concerns for most nations in the world due to environmental impact of CO₂ emission on the atmosphere contributing global warming. It has been realized that the green house emission from widespread utilization of fossil fuels has a deleterious effect on climate temperature. Consequently, there is a growing trend towards exploiting alternative, renewable and environmentally friendly fuels which are cost-wise competitive with fossil fuels (Vasudevan *et al.*, 2010).

Plant biomass, agricultural residues and forest wastes have received much attention as feedstock for the production of fuels which are known as biofuels. Biofuels could help decrease global demands for fossil fuels resulting reduction of greenhouse gas emission and environmental warming (Goh *et al.*, 2010). This research study is aimed at highlighting biomass resources, different type of biofuel (first and second generation of biofuels) and biotechnological process used for biofuels production.

Biomass is known as an organic, non-fossil material with a biological origin including plants, agricultural residues, forest wastes, microbial cells and municipal wastes derived from biological sources all which represent a potential sustainable energy source (Wu *et al.*, 2010). Agro-industrial residues obtained in food bioprocess constitute the large sources of biomass such as palm kernel cake produced in palm oil industry (Abdeshahian *et al.*, 2010a). The total amount of biomass produced on the Earth is approximated 100 billion tones organic dry matter of land biomass

annually and 50 billion tons of aquatic biomass (Naik et al., 2010).

Lignocellulose is the most plentiful renewable biomass which forms approximately half of the plant matter produced by photosynthesis indicating a vast sustainable organic resource in soil.

Lignocellulose is composed of three sorts of biopolymers to be specific, cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin that are emphatically connected by non-covalent strengths and by covalent cross linkages with a moderately moo substance of monosaccharides, starch, protein, or oils. As it were a little portion of the lignocellulosic substances gotten in horticulture or ranger service is utilized as nourishment, nourish, mechanical crude materials and vitality assets, the rest being considered squander reused to the Soil framework (Sanchez, 2009). Lignocellulose is a potential feedstock for the production of biofuels, industrial enzymes, animal feed, bio fertilizers, and bio pesticide and bio promoter products. Lignocellulosic raw materials are also used in the paper industry (Tangerdy and Szakacs, 2003). Lignocellulosic raw materials are also used in the production of industrial enzymes (Abdeshahian et al., 2010b).

Plant biomass has been realized as a major non-fossil resource of energy due to sustainable development of plant biomass for biotechnological applications, positive effect on global warming with the mitigation of atmospheric CO₂ and making independency to fossil fuel energy (Demirbas, 2007). In the sector of bioenergy production plant biomass has been known for decades as one of the most potentially renewable energy sources that could be utilized for the production of biofuels. Moreover, plant biomass can contribute to provide approximate 14% the total world's energy demand representing a key role for global economy (Zhao et al., 2009).

The term of biofuel refers to liquid fuels and blending components produced from renewable biological products (biomass) for using preliminary in the transport sector (Wu *et al.*, 2010). Biofuels are considered as a favorite, green alternative to fossil sources of energy offering several advantages including compatibility used in transportation infrastructure, contribution to mitigating carbon dioxide emissions, sustainability in production, plant biomass-based origin, security of supply and development of rural economy (Reijnders, 2006; Yan and Lin, 2009). Biotechnological efforts in 21nd century have been aimed at finding industrial feedstock and green processes for the production of biofuels and bio products using renewable biomass sources (Stevens and Verhe, 2004).

The massive energy crunch triggered by the 1973 oil price hike led to the revival of interest in non-conventional and renewable energy sources worldwide. Thus, along with

the solar and the wind energy, the long neglected but potentially rich biomass became the focus of intensive utilization for energy generation (Robertson, 1981). The increase in greenhouse gas emissions and the resulting climatic changes have understandably caused worldwide concern. According to an assessment by the Intergovernmental Panel on climate change (Watson, 2001); the rise in the average temperature by the end of the next century, i.e., 2100 will be between 1 - 3.5 °C. This has serious implications on the entire ecosystem. This fact has led to a series of initiatives at the international level to develop eco-friendly alternatives that would meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the abilities of future generations. This calls for urgent measures for minimizing, if not replacing, the reliance on fossil fuels to meet the increasing energy requirements. Therefore, the non-conventional renewable sources of energy have become the focus of research.

Wood and other forms of biomass are one of the main renewable energy sources available and provide liquid, solid and gaseous fuels. The global potential of primary biomass (in about 50 years) is very broad, quantified at $33-1135 \times 10^{15} \text{ Jy}^{-1}$ (Hoogwijk et al, 2003). But for biomass to effectively compete with fossil fuel there is need to explore more economic sources of biomass. Biomass waste is really cheap; in fact millions of dollars are used for its disposal annually. It is therefore of great interest to present one of the possibilities of converting these problematic wastes into ecologically friendly fuels.

The use of biomass as fuels help to reduce the greenhouse gas emission because the CO_2 released during combustion or conversion of biomass to chemicals is that removed from the environment by photosynthesis during the production of the biomass (i.e. plant growth).

The initial aim of this work was to improve the use of CO_2 in biomass-derived oil (BDO) reforming to syn-gas and other value-added chemical substances. An earlier research on BDO gasification in CO_2/N_2 system coined this objective (Panigrahi, 2003). In that study, it was observed that there was a significant decrease in the mole fraction of CO_2 in the product gas due to increase in the mole fraction of CO_2 in the feed gas. However, in this present research, it was observed that increasing CO_2 in the feed rather increased its mole fraction in the product gas.

2. Methodology

2.1 Pyrolysis and CO₂ Reforming of BDO

The BDO used for this study was obtained from Dyna Motive Energy Systems Company, Vancouver, Canada, where rapid wood pyrolysis technology was used to make it. Before any sample was taken for analysis or experiment the BDO was thoroughly mixed. This was achieved to guarantee sample uniformity.

2.1.2 Analysis of products

The product gas was analyzed for its composition using two GCs (Hewlett Packard 5890 series II and Carle GC-500 series). The Hewlett Packard 5890 II was equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and CarboSieve S II column (3000 mm, 3.18 mm i.d.) And it analysed H₂, CO, CO₂ and CH₄, whereas the Carle GC equipped with a flame ionization detector and a capillary column was used to analyses for hydrocarbons. The programs used in the GCs are given in Table 3. Standard gas mixtures were used for the calibration. After normalization of the components, the weight of the gas product was calculated from the moles of the components and the total volume of gas evolved during the run. The condensate was not analyzed.

2.2 Pyrolysis and Steam Reforming of Lard

2.2.1 Feed analysis

The lard used in this study was produced by Sobeys in Toronto, and was obtained from a retail outlet. The elemental analysis of the lard was performed on a CHN analyzer (Perkin Elmer 2400). The CHN analyzer did not detect traces of nitrogen which were known to be present in animal fats. Therefore, the ANTEK 9000 Combustion analyzer coupled to an ANTEK 738 Robotic Auto-sampler was used to analyze for Sulphur and nitrogen. The wt.% of O₂ in the lard was obtained by difference.

The lard's fatty acid composition was determined by POS Pilot Plant Corporation, Saskatoon, using gas chromatography. This was done by converting the fatty acids in the lard to their corresponding methyl esters and analyzing the resultant liquid with GC equipped with DB-FFAP column and flame ionization detector. The determination was according to AOCs standard method Ca 5a-40 (1997).

2.3 Gas Product Analysis

GC Hewlett Packard 5890 II was used to analyze for H₂, CO and CO₂ while Hewlett Packard 5880A equipped with a flame ionization detector and a Chromosorb102 column (1800 mm, 3.18 mm i.d.) was used to analyses for hydrocarbons. The same programming used for Carle GC500 was used for Hewlett Packard 5880A.

2.4 Liquid Product Analysis

2.4.1 Gas chromatographic analysis

The liquid product was first injected into an FID Varian 3400 GC equipped with a capillary column (DB-1, 100% dimethylpolysiloxane, 26 m x 0.32 mm) to obtain analytical chromatograms. Over 240 peaks were observed. The compounds present in the liquid product were then identified using a VG70-250-VSE mass-spectrometer (VG Analytical, Manchester, England) coupled to a Fisons GC 8000 series, Model 8060 (Fisons Instrument, Italy) which was equipped with a DB 5/MS (5% diphenyl, 95% dimethyl polysiloxane) capillary column (30 mm long and 0.25 mm i.e.).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Determination of Spray Pattern into the Reactor

The nourish channel was outlined to permit the nourish to splash on the quartz bed as depicted in point 2. Figure 1 appears the splash design gotten at two carrier gas temperatures and stream rates. It is watched from Figure 4.1 that the stream rate of carrier gas contains a noteworthy impact on splash design and bead measure of the reactant. The bead estimate was gotten by taking the normal of the sizes of any five spots taken at irregular from the design made. As the carrier gas flow rate was increased from 30 to 60 cm³ /min at 25°C (Figures 1), the droplet size of the reactant reduced from approximately 2.5 to 1.5 mm. At 50 °C and 30 cm³ /min (Figure 1), the droplet size was decreased further to 0.5 mm. At 50 °C and 60 cm³ /min (Figure 1.), the central broad spot completely disappeared and the droplet size was reduced to appr 0.2 mm. Since the temperature at the reactor entrance during each run was higher than 50 °C (approximately 200 °C), the droplet size would definitely be finer than the observed size in this spray test.

Figure 1. Spray pattern of BDO (5 g/h) generated by carrier gas

3.2 Characterization of BDO

As obtained from the supplier's MSDS, the BDO contains 25 wt.% water, 25 wt.% lignin and a balance of 50 wt.% of other oxygenated compounds. Its specific gravity and pH are 2.2-3.5 and 1.1-1.25, respectively. The viscosity was not given and thus was obtained using Brookfield Digital Viscometer model DV-1+. The result is given in Table 1. It is observed that the viscosity of the BDO ranged from 5.2 to 16.2 cSt over a temperature range of 25 to 80 °C. A viscosity of 6 CST at 80 °C was given on Dyna Motive website. The carbon (C), hydrogen (H) and nitrogen (N) analysis of the BDO was performed on a CHN analyzer (Perkin Elmer 2400) and the results are given in Table 2. The wt.% of O₂ in the BDO was obtained by difference.

3.3 Pyrolysis and CO₂ Reforming of BDO in a Fixed Bed Reactor

This area depicts the impacts of home time and CO₂ mole division within the carrier gas on item yields, gas composition and warming esteem. Within the consider by Panigrahi et al. (2003), they watched most elevated change at 800 °C for pyrolysis of BDO. Subsequently, all the runs here were done at a temperature of 800 °C. The watched fabric adjust was within the extend of 90 – 96 wt.%.

Table1. Viscosity of BDO

Temperature (°C)	Viscosity (cP)	Viscosity (cSt)*
25	18.6	16.2
40	16.9	14.7
80	6.0	5.2

* obtained at a specific gravity of 1.15

Table 2. CHN analysis of the BDO

Component	wt%
C	35.3
H	8.3
N	0.4
O*	56.0

*obtained by difference

4.1 Physical and Chemical Properties of Lard

The physical properties of the fat as well as its greasy corrosive composition are given in Table 3. The procedures utilized to get these properties were examined in area 3.5.2. The information in Table 3 demonstrate that the bolster contains a tall warming esteem (39.6 MJ/kg) and thickness (36.4 mPa.s). Moreover, the fat contained huge amounts of palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic corrosive moieties. The natural investigation of the fat gave 77.3 wt.% C, 12.2 wt.% H, 10.5 wt.% O. Follows of sulfur (~ 32 wppm) and nitrogen (~ 8 wppm) were too found. These follow sums of sulfur and nitrogen within the bolster is critical criteria for its application for fuel. It implies that the created fuel will not be mindful for SO_x and NO_x emanation both of which are undesirable in combustion forms.

Table 3. Physical and chemical properties of the feed (lard)

Physical properties	
Density @40°C (kg/m ³)	940
Heat of combustion (MJ/kg)	39.6
Viscosity @40°C (mPa.s)	36.4
CHNS/O analysis, wt% (wppm)	
C	77.3
H	12.2
N	0.0008 (8)
S	0.0032 (32)
O*	10.5
Composition, wt% of total fatty acids**	
C10:0 (Capric)	0.1
C12:0 (Lauric)	0.1
C14:0 (Myristic)	1.4
C15:0 (Pentadecanoic)	0.1
C16:0 (Palmitic)	24.1
C16:1 (Palmitoleic)	2.4
C17:0 (Magaric)	0.4
C18:0 (Stearic)	14.0
C18:1 (Oleic)	39.4
C18:2 (Linoleic)	14.2
C18:3 (alpha-Linolenic)	0.8
C18:4 (Octadecatetraenoic)	0.1
C20:0 (Arachidic)	0.2
C20:1 (Eicosenoic)	0.7
C20:2 (Eicosadienoic)	0.5
Others	1.4

*obtained by difference **xx:y: xx number of carbon atoms; y number of double bonds

Figure2. Thermo-Gravimetric/Differential Thermo-Gravimetric plots for lard

4.2 Pyrolysis of Lard

Pyrolysis refers to a chemical change caused by the application of thermal energy in the absence of oxygen (Scott and Piskorz, 1982). The pyrolysis products of lard were gas, liquid and char. It was possible to determine CO, CO₂, and most of the C1-C4 hydrocarbon components (such as methane, ethylene, propane, propylene, isobutene, isobutylene, and 1-butene) in the gas product from GC analysis alone. Isobutene, isobutylene, and 1-butene) in the gas product from GC analysis alone.

Table 4. Reproducibility of results during pyrolysis of lard

(N₂: 50 cm³/min, quartz particle size: 0.7-1.4 mm, lard: 5g/h, temperature: 550 °C)

	1	2	4	Mean ± SEM
Product gas composition, mol %				
H ₂	0	0	0	0.00±0.0
CO	9.4	9.8	10.6	9.9±0.3
CO ₂	4.6	4.5	5.1	4.7±0.2
CH ₄	8.4	9.5	9.5	9.1±0.2
C ₂ H ₄	21.6	24.6	24.6	23.6±0.6
C ₂ H ₆	7.3	7.8	8	7.7±0.1
C ₃ H ₆	10	15.6	15.6	13.7±1.1
C ₃ H ₈	1.1	1	1.1	1.1±0.0
Gas heating value MJ/m ³	147.6	135.8	131.6	138.3±2.7
Liquid product characterization				
Diesel-like liquid product g/100g lard	28.1	30.7	31.4	30.1±2.0
Cetane Index	50.3	52.3	49.3	50.6±1.0
Density kg/m ³ @25°C	880	875	880	878.3±4.0
Viscosity mPa.s @40°C	10.6	9.5	11.1	10.4±0.5
Liquid heating value MJ/kg	40	39.5	39.9	39.8±0.1

Figure 3. Effects of residence time on products gas composition (Process: pyrolysis, temperature 600 °C, quartz packing height 70 mm, Size 1.7-2.4 mm, duration 30 min)

4.3 Steam Reforming of Lard

All the steam changing tests were conducted with the littler molecule estimate quartz (0.7-1.4 mm). The fluid item within the steam changing test alludes to the organic parcel of the whole condensate. The fluid layer was evacuated by decantation and analyzed for its water substance. The natural layer was too analyzed for its water substance. The mass of the fluid parcel was between 93.8 and 99.2 wt.% of the water pumped amid the try. The water substance of the fluid parcel extended between 97.5 and 99.8 wt.% whereas that of the natural parcel extended between 0.85 and 1.12 wt.%.

Table 5. Effects of duration of experiment on pyrolysis of lard (N₂ flow rate 50 cm³/min (STP), packing particle height 70 mm and size 0.7-1.4 mm, Lard 5g/h, and Temperature 600°C)

	Duration of experiment, minutes	
	30	225
Product gas composition mol%		
H ₂	0	0
CO	9	10.9
CO ₂	3.6	4.7
CH ₄	11	12.0
C ₂ H ₄	27	27.2
C ₂ H ₆	7.6	8.0
C ₃ H ₆	17.1	17.2
C ₃ H ₈	0.8	0.9
C ₄ ⁺	24	19.1
Products yield (wt% of total product)		
Gas	39.8	51.7
Liquid	55.6	47.8
Char	4.5	0.45
Liquid product characterization		
Diesel-like liquid, g/100g lard	24.4	25.0
Cetane Index	45.8	45.9
Density kg/m ³	860	845
Viscosity, mPa.s	4.5	2.4

4.4 Fuel Properties of the Pyrolysis and Steam Reforming Liquid Products

The information collected from the characterization considers of the fluid item permitted for the comparison of the properties of this item with those of ordinary diesel powers. A comparison is appeared in table5.

Figure 4. GC/MS Chromatogram for the pyrolysis liquid obtained at a temperature of

550°C, carrier gas flow rate of 10 cm³/min and quartz height of 70 mm and particle size of 1.7-2.4 mm

The fluid item gotten through pyrolysis at 600 °C and 50 cm³ /min carrier gas (N₂) stream rate features a certain file of 46 and thickness of 860 kg/m³ at 25 °C, which are in assertion with the detail for diesel fuel. Be that as it may, the viscosity (4.5 mPa.s at 40 °C) surpasses the desired esteem of 3.5 mPa.s for diesel fuel. Too, the higher warming esteem of this fluid (~40 MJ/kg) is roughly 11% less than that of diesel fuel showing an impressive sum of oxygenated compounds within the fuel (Schwab et al., 1988). The cloud point is tall and well over that of diesel though the pour point is comparable to that of diesel.

Table 6 Comparison of products obtained from BDO and lard pyrolysis (temperature: 800°C, quartz packing height: 70mm, size: 1.7-2.4 mm, reaction time: 30 min)

Feed stock	Biomass-derived oil	Lard
Temperature °C	800	800
Q. particle size mm	1.7-2.4	1.7-2.4
Carrier gas (N ₂) cm ³ /min	30	30
Feed pumped	2.0	2.2
Condensate wt%	41.9	0
Char wt%	23.4	31.8
Gas wt%	34.8	67.2
Gas composition mol%		
H ₂	33.1	51.8
CO	39.9	10.4
CO ₂	5.9	10.3
CH ₄	14.4	11.4
C ₂ H ₄	5.5	10.1
C ₂ H ₆	0.6	2.5
C ₃ H ₆	0.4	2.7
C ₃ H ₈	0.03	0.1
C ₄₊	0.3	1.5
H ₂ +CO	73.0	62.2
H ₂ /CO	0.83	4.98
Heating Value MJ/m ³	22.1	30.5
Volume of gas L/100g feed	37.7	160.0

This is because the oxygenated compounds present interfere with the cloud point determination but did not interfere with that of pour point. A small amount of water (~ 0.5 wt. %) was found in the liquid product. The water could easily be removed or retained as the case may be. There are some beneficial consequences of the presence of water. It causes a decrease in viscosity (as observed in this study), lowers the combustion temperature and, as a consequence, lowers the NO_x emission (Diebold, 1997).

5. Conclusion

Renewable resources and bio-based feedstocks will provide a sustainable alternative to petrochemical sources to meet the ever-increasing demand for energy and chemicals in modern society. Nonetheless, the processes of conversion needed for these future bio-refineries are likely to differ from those currently used in the petrochemical industry. Biotechnology and chemo catalysis provide routes to transform biomass into a range of molecules which can act as chemical platforms. While a host of technologies can be leveraged for biomass upgrading, condensation reactions are significant because they have the potential to upgrade these bio-derived feedstocks while minimizing the loss of carbon and the generation of by-products. This article surveys both the biological and chemical catalytic routes to producing platform chemicals from renewable sources and describes advances in condensation chemistry and strategies for the conversion of these platform chemicals into fuels and high-value chemicals. This research focused on two main feed stocks (BDO and lard) and their conversion to value added products. The main objective of the study on BDO was to use CO₂ for its reforming thereby finding a sink for the greenhouse gas (CO₂). BDO has been converted to synthesis gas and medium heating value gaseous fuel by CO₂ reforming. The product gas consisted mostly of H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and C₂H₄. Composition of product gas ranged between synthesis gas 61-76 mol%, CH₄ 3-18 mol%, and C₂H₄ 1-6.5 mol%. In all cases, the output of synthesis gas was high (> 60 mol per cent) with or without CO₂ addition. Maximum synthesis gas output (~76 mol percent) was observed at a 60 cm³/min total carrier gas flow rate and a 0.1 mole CO₂ fraction in carrier gas. The maximum gas production (51 wt. %) was observed at a total carrier gas flow rate of 30 cm³ /min containing 20 mol% of CO₂. A diesel-like liquid has been produced from pyrolysis and steam reforming of lard in the absence of a catalyst. This study also identifies animal fats as a source of high calorific value (68 -165 MJ/m³) gaseous fuel. Lard was converted to liquid product containing diesel boiling range hydrocarbons and gas product which consists mostly of C₁-C₃ hydrocarbons, CO, CO₂ and H₂ by pyrolysis and steam reforming.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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